

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To overcome the global recession, some companies cut resources and laid off workers, while others adopted better strategies to improve processes and change culture. Unfortunately, there remains a gap between successful and less successful companies in terms of process management, people management and the adaptability of culture. Culture drives competitive advantage in companies like Toyota, which has a psychology of process improvement unlike its competitors. Toyota's lessons can help other organizations change the routines of thinking and acting to teach employees how to improve.

A new routine for culture change

BY MOHAMMED HAMED AHMED SOLIMAN

In his book *Toyota Kata*, Mike Rother wrote that none outside of the Toyota group of companies has successfully brought systematic continuous improvement into all processes every day and across the organization. Even Toyota's efforts to spread its approach of continuous improvement to outside suppliers have not met expectations.

Truly, most organizations remain far away from establishing a solid continuous improvement system, and current management behavior rarely leads corporations to do what they should do in terms of both process and people management. Bad habits, or behaviors done with little or no conscious thought, continue to affect culture and hold companies back from success.

Recruiting the right habits

One of the initial steps for business success is getting the right people on board with the appropriate skills and attitudes. How companies choose and hire their people reflect their organizational culture. These hires are going to develop new methods of working, invent new products, lead the transformation and build a successful business. They are the company's future leaders.

But do companies really get what they expect from their hiring candidates?

Traditionally, companies demand degrees and certifications to demonstrate expertise, while others prefer to hire based on experience, history and skills. Neither way will work if the organization in question refuses to develop a culture of improvement. Managers hire MBAs and Six Sigma black belts with the mistaken notion that they will transform the business without a transformation of management.

Yet what can a certificate holder do in a system that doesn't engage employees in the continuous improvement cycle, value their ideas and develop them continuously? A closer look at these companies reveals that they don't have a real system capable of utilizing and

aligning employee skills and efforts to solve problems and achieve business goals. Your entire professional force can get certified, but if the company culture doesn't allow it, they won't get the chance to practice what they have learned.

And while certificates can prove ability, actual improvement will not occur without a high commitment to self-education and self-development to keep the certificate holder's knowledge up to date, allowing the person to develop better ways of working and practicing. Certificates don't drive performance competency in the practical world.

Josh Kaufman, author of the international best-seller *Personal MBA*, wrote that a large body of evidence suggests that what some business schools teach has no connection to what is required for business success.

Unfortunately, according to Kaufman, many business programs have de-emphasized value creation and operations in favor of finance and quantitative analysis.

This extreme focus on financial analysis produces executives who are not capable of improving business performance, driving success and creating value for customers. It doesn't build distinguished leadership.

Reinforced by their MBA education, many executives and managers seek solid financial outcomes, although in many instances they have lost connection with the reality that exists on their organization's front lines. Decision-makers are poorly informed about the actual situation, and decision-making is based on incorrect assumptions and inappropriate targets. They have learned to manage the process via distance using some reported metrics. They have not been taught the culture of improvement.

For example, if managers remain behind the scenes and avoid the actual place where the work is done (the gemba), they will not realize what small issues pop up as obstacles to success. They will make poor decisions. Then,

when their business processes fail, the human resources department asks what went wrong. After all, they have hired professional, qualified persons.

But hiring professionals won't, by itself, turn around an organization. Having a real continuous improvement system and an embedded culture of improvement will. A system that empowers employees to make changes, motivates them in the right way, aligns goals and efforts with organizational strategies and vision, develops leaders continuously, bases management decisions on real situations, and makes improvement a part of everyone's daily routine is a system with a high chance of success.

Better questions, better results

When organizations base their hiring processes on certifications and classic interviews, what do the companies really know about these individuals, their behaviors and their openness to change? Do companies really get the results they need?

The hiring process can be improved to select better candidates if the human resources department, instead of asking for certifications, tests individuals properly and assesses their skills.

Toyota approaches the hiring process differently. The powerhouse Japanese automaker wants to hire people who are motivated and highly committed to self-development and self-education. For Toyota to exceed customer expectations, its employees must do the same. Toyota tends to assess what its candidates know and how they are going to use that knowledge.

Jeffrey K. Liker's *The Toyota Way to Lean Leadership* originally reported that when Toyota started to hire leaders for the New United Motor Manufacturing Inc. (NUMMI) plant, the first joint venture plant between Toyota and General Motors, the focus was on hiring candidates who had demonstrated an inherent capacity for self-development and learning. Toyota wanted people who had an openness and excitement to learning new things.

Certificates don't drive performance competency in the practical world.

Toyota also uses a system to test individuals for their abilities to work in a team. A group of candidates is placed in a meeting room and assigned a problem to solve. Toyota likes to hire the candidates who demonstrate the ability to function well in a team and devise a solution by working with others.

Organizations should use behavior-based tests and real assessments as part of any recruitment strategy. And this is where the application of industrial and organization psychology comes in.

In the book *Social Psychology and Human Nature*, authors Roy F. Baumeister and Brad J. Bushman reported that most companies use informal and unstructured behavioral interview questions like the following:

- What are your weaknesses?
- Why should we hire you?
- Why do you want to work here?
- What are your goals?
- Why are you leaving your job?
- When were you most satisfied in your job?
- What can you do for us that other candidates can't?
- What are three positive things your last boss can say about you?
- What salary are you seeking?

According to many psychologists and researchers, such traditional questions don't serve a company's real needs. Improving the hiring process to help generate a culture of change would involve using relative, reasonable and structured behavior questions such as these:

- Tell me in specific detail about a time when you had to deal with a difficult customer.
- Give me an example of a time when you had to make a decision without a supervisor present.
- Give me a specific example when you demonstrated an initiative in an employment setting.
- Give me an example of a time when you had to work in a team.

- Describe a time when you had to be creative at solving a problem.

Such questions tend to assess leadership and problem-solving skills, which is what most companies really need anyway.

Embedding improvement into the day

Often, employees don't focus on improvement because of the lack of "north goals" and the improper alignment of departmental goals with the organization's strategies and vision.

In the Toyota vision, "north goals" refer to the long-term vision, such as being the best automotive maker in the world or holding more than 50 percent of the market share. In *Toyota Kata*, Rother calls the process of setting targets and striving toward them in Toyota the "improvement kata," and management focuses each day on coaching employees on how to reach those targets – targets that are aligned with the company's long-term vision.

A kata is a series of practice moves to build on form and technique. For our leaders, we want them to be able to do two things: Systematically improve processes toward a clear target (improvement kata) and coach others on the improvement kata (coaching kata).

Improvement kata really describes the Toyota habits for continuous improvement. Toyota uses its improvement kata to make a way of managing and working that we normally reserve for crisis situations. And the more often employees practice these new improvement behaviors, the more likely they will become routine.

Concrete, stretch goals, aligned with organizational strategies, are the key to making improvement a priority. Stretch goals break down strategic goals into easy to understand bites that workers can digest and are a main way to cascade organizational values down from above to the front lines. For example, it means nothing to tell your employees that the goal is to be

the leading supplier in the industry. But breaking that aim down into stretch goals yields metrics, such as "50 percent reduction in defects per year," or "20 percent productivity gain each year," that can measure results.

By repeating the continuous improvement cycle and using smaller stretch goals, organizations can achieve their long-term vision. Departmental goals should be aligned with the company's strategic objectives, or the employees will wonder why they are bothering to improve the system. People tend to make progress on things they believe in. It is a part of any motivation program.

The more often employees practice these new improvement behaviors, the more likely they will become routine. People should believe in the power of the system and that they are working to make their job and life easier and safer. The company's success is their success. This is where the intrinsic motivation comes from. If goals are not specified, people won't improve because they will think everything is fine.

But if the company has clear strategic goals, goals that are broken down into achievable metrics, employees will generate ideas and explain how their ideas are aligned with these goals. The system itself will drive the motivation and creativity of everyone. There will be no more need for financial motives that undermine performance and kill motivation. A system that trains supervisors and engineers to listen to the workers' problems and allows information can be exceptionally motivational.

When psychology gets in the way

Think of your vision in business terms – such as No. 1 market share, zero warranty cost and 100 percent accountability. Break those down into stretch goals for your employees and departments to use. Make sure these stretch goals are concrete and aligned with your strategic business objectives by aligning them with the value you provide to your customers.

Goals can't be things like standardizing the work process, which simply opens up the workforce's psychology to

a host of questions. The human mind always seems to latch on to criticism of change. Workers will wonder why they are standardizing the work. After all, they're OK with the current process. Why should we put forth energy and effort instead of focusing on a higher priority? If improvement doesn't have a clear direction and assigned priority, people will consider it low priority and continue with their current methods.

As explained in *Toyota Kata*, Toyota inserted continuous improvement into its employee DNA by using the kata approach. Improvement became a part of each employee's daily routine, something that can't be achieved through formal training or classrooms.

Take, for example, the question "What do you want to do to improve your work?" The answer can be "We need to reduce setup times, apply a production pull system, remove wastes from the shop floor, reduce production lead-times and standardize work procedures." This is what most companies do, and it represents a poor alignment of goals with strategies.

Lean improvement, on the other hand, strives toward an objective. A better question would be "What is your target?" The answer could be "Meeting the customer demand rate (takt time)." This begs the question of what do the workers need to do to reach this target, which yields the answer that they need to improve the cycle time of their machines to meet the customer takt time.

The second case clearly defines customer takt time as a stretch goal to strive for. We know where we want to be. And improving machine cycle time is a target condition that we must meet to reach our goal. It should be a measurable thing, like a cycle time of 50 seconds faster than the takt time. The first example has no target, and we could spin our wheels improving things while not knowing where we want to be or where this improvement will lead us.

One of the most fundamental mistakes made by many companies is trying to improve something without a

clear strategy that serves the customer requirements and finally the success of the business. But meeting the customer demand rate will allow the organization to deliver products on time and achieve 100 percent customer satisfaction. This can serve the long-term strategic objective of being a leading supplier.

People and core values

You will need a strategy statement that articulates your vision and incorporates the stretch goals that are required to achieve it. Even if your people don't fully understand where you are taking them, repeating the words of your strategy will help them understand that they are part of a team going in the same direction.

These statements should be generic enough that your vision will fit any future acquisitions. It is important that your strategy defines the operational excellence that you envision, visions such as be the leading supplier in your industry or be one of the globe's top 10 corporations.

Core values must be articulated. Achieving excellence requires teamwork, trust and respect for people. Core values are like guideposts that will point your workforce toward your ultimate goal of working in a culture of improvement.

The three main core values to consider are people, customer and quality. Respect for people is one of the Toyota production system's pillars and is the main reason for Toyota's success.

A policy of not laying off employees because of improving efficiency is a good thing to follow. Letting workers go after they improve a process will disrupt the whole system, and it means no improvement next time. Employees will resist change as long as it threatens their livelihoods. If a strategy of respect for people is set, then a 20 percent cost reduction target clearly means process improvement, not cutting resources. Always remember that a company can't change its core values every few years without losing the respect and confidence of its people.

Respect for people includes

developing your leaders instead of outsourcing solutions. Many companies hire external experts. They create a continuous improvement department, hire the improvement consultants and relegate the improvement behavior to them. Such a parallel team will be powerless to effect change and make improvement. They don't know the company's culture or processes.

And when the outsourced consultant leaves, all knowledge is gone. The regular employees have no experience to keep managing the improved processes or continuously improving them to face the future challenges. They have not been trained on the culture of continuous improvement and have not contributed to the transformation process.

Instead, lean tools should be used by the company's leaders and the factory managers who have the capability, power and responsibility to effect changes. Improvement should be done by people who are managing the work day by day, not by a parallel team. The leaders who manage work each day will be responsible for coaching people who do the work. And those people must own, operate, develop and continually improve their processes. Companies that travel the consultant route should make sure they use the temporary personnel to share lean expertise and knowledge with the rest of the workforce.

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Classroom vs. continuous coaching

We learn by doing, and problems give us lessons to learn. What we learn through formal educational programs can't be standardized for all industries and cultures. What might work in one place won't work in another. Situations differ, even in the same industry. Anyway, classroom training, while it can only provide a specific level of awareness, does not change behaviors and culture.

Toyota uses a completely different pattern of learning. Toyota teaches its workers to develop solutions, not just

to solve problems. The automaker's employees learn a routine of thinking and acting that harnesses the human capability to improve.

Many companies aim to teach their employees skills, delegating the process to the training department or human resources. Those departments might assess what employees know, their performance, and train them accordingly.

Instead, as a commitment to self-education and continuous development, Toyota's kata system continuously develops people and ensures that each mentee has a mentor. For example, the team member is coached

by the team leader, and the team leader is coached by the group leader. This is Toyota's method for passing its improvement kata on to all organization members.

Continuous coaching at the workplace builds strong leaders. Embedding this into the organization's daily routine will make improvement a habit of everyone. This is a main reason why continuous improvement becomes a behavior pattern for everyone in Toyota's organizations. The learning cycles that Toyota leaders have to take, the continuous coaching at the workplace, and the utilization of problems as an opportunity to

learn and grow have made Toyota a remarkable company.

As Liker explained in *Toyota Under Fire*, this is what allowed Toyota to come out stronger after several recall crises in the 2000s. It helped Toyota stand out during the global recession. Toyota doesn't rely on certifications and formal education programs. In fact, Japanese business culture doesn't think much of such certifications and MBAs because management and leadership should be taught at the gemba, where the actual work is done. This is where Toyota and many other Japanese businesses conduct most of their training.

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Toyota's kata system is one of the best strategies ever created to learn and develop leaders. As Rother presented in *Toyota Kata*, Toyota specifies, aligns and achieves the outcome targets via the improvement kata behavior. This process removes obstacles and keeps repeating the plan-do-check-act (PDCA) cycle at every step. At the same time, Toyota's coaching kata coaches people on how to achieve their goals and meet target conditions. Toyota is teaching people across the organization a behavior routine that aligns people and functions in accordance with the company's philosophy and vision.

So how about you?

Start with a vision. For struggling businesses, a long-term vision of five or 10 years won't mean much if the company ceases to exist in 12 months. In this case, targets should be adapted to match the real situation to help the company survive.

Goals can be broken down into

more manageable pieces and smaller increments. This ensures quality implementation. You also can apply the PDCA cycle slowly at every step and remove obstacles as they are found. It is preferable not to apply a large improvement at once. The obstacles and resistance to such change would be huge, and the entire program could fail quickly.

For each target, specify the current condition and the target condition using the appropriate metric. In many conditions, setting and trying to follow a long-term plan for making improvements is like moving in a road full of fog. Breaking the goals into smaller, stretch targets makes them easier to manage, motivating your workers to strive for success. Specify a plan for reaching each target, make it actionable and give it a time frame. Get your people involved in how to do it, and listen to their ideas carefully.

It is important not to neglect the training. Most companies that fail to

reach their improvement goals have neglected the training and coaching, which are necessary parts of the process. Managers should dig deep in the details to discover root causes rather than jumping to solutions and the "do" phase in the continuous improvement cycle.

Changing cultures and breaking old habits are the keys to better performance. Cultural behaviors drive competency, company growth and continual success. Organizations need to change their culture if they want to embed continuous improvement into everyone's daily routine.

It is easy to talk about and hard to do. It requires long-term management support and internal investment.

Changing cultures and breaking old habits are the keys to better performance. Practicing new behaviors will shift the employees out of the existing routine and, over time, influence people's thoughts and actions. In the long term, repeated new habits can lead to a culture of continuous improvement. ❖

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